

Illiterate Mothers; a Common Risk Factor of Severe Anemia among Children below 10 Years of Age

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To determine common risk factors of severe anemia among children below 10 years of age

Design and duration: This is a prospective study completed in duration of eight months from July 2019 to February 2020

Setting: Study was conducted in Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur.

Patients & methods: Children below ten years of age presenting to the study hospital with the complaint of severe anemia were included in the study. These cases were not having any obvious other morbidity causing anemia. Complete blood count and blood morphology was done in every child. Hemoglobin level below 7g/dl was taken as severe anemia in this study. Confidence interval was 95%, margin of error 5%. P-value less than 0.05 was taken significant. Percentages, frequencies, means and standard deviation calculated using SPSS software. Results presented via tables and graphs. Consent was taken from guardians of children for including their children in the study. Educational status of mothers was determined.

Results: Total 75 children having anemia were studied. Age range was 6months to 10 years with mean age of 4.7±3.2 years. There were 24% cases between 25-36 months. In most of the children 56% hemoglobin was 5-6 g/dl. Mostly mothers were having education below matriculation.

Conclusion: Illiteracy among mothers of our country is a common risk factor of severe anemia in their children. Increasing literacy rate can reduce incidence of this disease and nutritional status of children and nursing mothers can be improved as well.

Key words: Anemia, illiterate mothers, anemic children

INTRODUCTION

Anemia among children is much common problem in developing and underdeveloped countries. Our country is also having high rate of malnourished children. Low economic status of country influences greatly on prevalence of this problem. On the other hand literacy rate is a very important

risk factor contributing to this problem. Mothers should be educated because they have to feed their children and health of children depends greatly on behavior and health related awareness of mothers. Initially in 1995 anemic children were 47% worldwide with decreasing its rate to 43% in 2011. According to a study anemia is present in 62% preschool going children and severe anemia is found in 5.5% children in Pakistan. This anemia is due to deficiency of iron. Improper eating habits of nursing mothers and feeding their children iron deficient foods is a cause of it. Iron deficiency not only causes anemia but also decreases cognitive abilities, mental and physical growth.

Patients & methods

This is a cross sectional study conducted in a tertiary care hospital located in Bahawalpur city named Bahawal Victoria Hospital. Study was started in July 2019 and completed after eight months in February 2020. Children below ten years of age presenting to the study hospital with the complaint of severe anemia were included in the study. These cases were not having any obvious other morbidity causing anemia. Complete blood count and blood morphology was done in every child. Hemoglobin level below 7g/dl was taken as severe anemia in this study. Confidence interval was 95%, margin of error 5%. P-value less than 0.05 was taken significant. Percentages, frequencies, means and standard deviation calculated using SPSS software. Results presented via tables and graphs. Consent was taken from guardians of children for including their children in the study. Educational status of mothers was determined. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied in selecting the children for study purpose. Sampling technique was consecutive convenient sampling.

Results

Total 75 children having anemia were studied. Age range was 6months to 10 years with mean age of 4.7±3.2 years. There were 18(24%) cases between

25-36 months, 15(20%) between 6-12 months, 22(29.3%) between 13-24 months and 9(12%) between 49-60 months of age. In most of the children 42(56%) hemoglobin was 5-6 g/dl, in

13(17.3%) between 4-5g/dl and in 20(26.7%) cases HB level was 6-7 g/dl. There were mostly mothers were having education below matriculation.

Education level among mothers of children under study

DISCUSSION

According to WHO 300 million children worldwide was having anemia in 2011. Mothers should be educated because they have to feed their children and health of children depends greatly on behavior and health related awareness of mothers. Initially in 1995 anemic children were 47% worldwide with decreasing its rate to 43% in 2011. According to a study anemia is present in 62% preschool going children and severe anemia is found in 5.5% children in Pakistan. This anemia is due to deficiency of iron. Improper eating habits of nursing mothers and feeding their children iron deficient foods is a cause of it. Iron deficiency not only causes anemia but also decreases cognitive abilities, mental and physical growth. This is a cross sectional study conducted in a tertiary care hospital located in Bahawalpur city named Bahawal Vitoria Hospital. Total 75 children having anemia were studied. Age range was

6months to 10 years with mean age of 4.7±3.2 years. There were 18(24%) cases between 25-36 months, 15(20%) between 6-12 months, 22(29.3%) between 13-24 months and 9(12%) between 49-60 months of age. Study was started in July 2019 and completed after eight moths i9n February 2020. Children below ten years of age presenting to the study hospital with the complaint of severe anemia were included in the study. These cases were not having any obvious other morbidity causing anemia. Complete blood count and blood morphology was done in every child. Hemoglobin level below 7g/dl was taken as severe anemia in this study. Confidence interval was 95%, margin of error 5%. P-value less than 0.05 was taken significant.

Conclusion: Illiteracy among mothers of our country is a common risk factor of severe anemia in their children. Increasing literacy rate can reduce incidence of this disease and nutritional status of children and nursing mothers can be improved as well.

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